

Quality Assessment of Well Water from Natmauk Township, Magway Region

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Abstract

In this research, three water samples were collected from near Ywamon Village in Natmauk Township, Magway Region to determine some physicochemical parameters {pH, temperature, total hardness, alkalinity, chlorinity, salinity, total dissolved solid (TDS), total suspended solid (TSS), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD)}. The toxic elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As and Cr) in samples were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS). Total coliforms contained in samples were determined by multiple tubes method in National Health Laboratory (NHL). The pH of the samples were determined by a pH meter. The total alkalinity, total hardness, chloride contents and COD were determined by titrimetric method. The total coliforms of collected water samples (>16 MPN) were higher than the WHO standard, 10 MPN (Most Probable Number/ 100 mL). According to the experimental results, it can be observed that the pH values of all water samples were 6.5 – 8.5, the acceptable pH for UNEP standard value. The alkalinity values of these samples were very high. The high values of hardness were also found in sample 3. According to the higher alkalinity, toxic elements and coliforms contents, these water samples should not be used as drinking water.

Keywords : Natmauk Township, Titrimetric method, pH meter, COD, AAS

Introduction

Water has always been a vital material for man's existence. The use for drinking, cooking, agriculture, transport, industry and recreation immediately shows the extent to which it is an integral part of life. People cannot exist without water, so there has always been a demand, and all the nearest and more obvious sources have already been exploited (Wilson, 1974). The important sources of natural water are rain water, stream water, ground water and river water, spring and well water, lake and pond water, and sea water. A simple alternative to a spring is a well, used when groundwater is close to the surface. A well is normally a vertical shaft, wide enough to allow access for a man to dig. It may be excavated by hand or with simple machinery. Deeper water can be exploited by drilling a borehole; these tend to be smaller diameter than a well, and are drilled using a drilling rig. There are many designs of rig, but they commonly use a mechanically operated chisel to break up the rock and water or air to flush the chippings to the surface, Confusingly the two words, well and borehole, are often used together. To raise groundwater to the surface we need to pump the water up from the well or borehole. Groundwater makes up nearly 70 % of all the world's freshwater; only 0.2 % is found in lakes, streams or rivers and 30 % is bound up in snow and ice on mountains and in the polar regions. Groundwater plays a number of very important roles in our environment and in our economy. One of the great benefits of using groundwater is that it is normally of good quality. The slow infiltration of water through soil and rocks acts as a natural filtration process, removing many potential contaminants, especially harmful bacteria.

Materials and Methods

Three water samples were collected from near Ywamon Village in Natmauk Township, Magway Region in month of June, 2012. Water samples were taken from 3 feet depth from the surface level. The locations of sampling site are mentioned in Table 1 and Figure 1. The sampling bottles and stoppers were carefully cleaned prior to each experimental run. These bottles had been washed with a detergent and rinsed with water, 1:1 nitric acid solution and distilled water. The data of water analysis is largely dependent on correct sampling.

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The collected water samples were immediately stored in air tight, narrow neck amber-coloured bottles and were stored in laboratory at 25°C prior to any investigations. For bacteriological investigation, water samples were collected by clean sterilized bottles.

The pH of water samples were determined by using pH meter (Model EIL-7020, ABB, Kent-Taylor Ltd., England). The temperature of the water samples were determined by using thermometer. The alkalinity of water samples were determined by titration of water samples with standard solution of sulphuric acid using phenolphthalein and methyl orange as indicator. Chlorinity of samples were determined by Mohr's modified method and converted into salinity by using Knudsen equation. The total hardness of samples were determined by EDTA titrimetric method. Total dissolved solids and total suspended solids of water samples were determined by gravimetric method. Dissolved oxygen contents of three water samples were determined by dissolved oxygen meter.

Chemical oxygen demand in water samples were determined by titrimetric method using potassium permanganate method. Toxic elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As and Cr) in three water samples were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Perkin Elmer Analyst, USA) in Asia Research Centre (ARC), University of Yangon. Total coliforms contained in three water samples were determined by multiple tubes method in National Health Laboratory (NHL).

Results and Discussion

In this study, three water samples were collected from near Ywamon Village in Natmawk Township, Magway Region in month of June, 2012. The pH of the water samples were determined by a pH meter. The pH values of three water samples were found to be in the range of 6.5 to 8.5 (Table 2). The acceptable pH for UNEP Standard is between 6.5 and 8.5. Thus, the pH values of all drinking water samples fall within the standard range.

Water bodies undergo temperature variations along with normal climatic fluctuations. The temperature of surface water is influenced by latitude, altitude, season, time of day, air circulation, cloud cover, the flow and depth of the water body. In turn, temperature affects physical, chemical and biological processes in water bodies (Singh, 2010). Temperature of the water samples were determined by a thermometer (GP-300°). The values were found to be in the range of 29.5 to 30°C (Table 2).

The total alkalinity of water samples were determined by titrimetric method. It was analysed by titrating water samples against standard acid solution using two indicator solutions. The allowable alkalinity for UNEP standard is 80-120 ppm (UNEP, 2004). It was found that the alkalinity values of water samples were found to be in the range of 480 to 1320 ppm (Table 3). These values were very higher alkalinity in the samples.

The total hardness of water samples were determined by EDTA titrimetric method. The total hardness for UNEP standard is maximum 300 ppm. The observed values of water samples were found to be in the range of 255.1 to 318.8 ppm (Table 3). The high values of total hardness were found to be sample 3.

The chloride contents of water samples were determined by Mohr's titration using a standard solution of silver nitrate and potassium chromate indicator. The chloride contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 53.19 to 241.13 ppm (Table 3). The guideline value for chloride in drinking water is 250 ppm (UNEP, 2004). The salinity contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.190 to 0.465 ppt (Table 3). UNEP standard for freshwater salinity is < 3 ppt. Thus, the chloride contents and salinity contents of all drinking water samples fall within the standard range.

Total dissolved solids of water samples were determined by conventional gravimetric method. TDS values of water samples were found to be in the range of 360 to 2660 ppm (Table 4). The standard value of TDS for drinking water is 300 ppm (UNEP, 2004). Thus, the determined values of samples were higher than the standard value.

Total suspended solids of water samples were determined by filtration method. The values were found to be in the range of 600 to 1100 ppm (Table 4). The total suspended solids for UNEP standard is maximum 400 ppm. The higher values of total suspended solids were found to be all samples.

Dissolved oxygen contents of three water samples were determined by DO meter. The standard values of DO were in the range of 4-8 ppm (UNEP, 2004). The observed values of water samples were found to be 4.53 to 7.11 ppm (Table 5) which is within the permissible limit. DO is an important determinant for stability of water and survival of water organisms. The critical oxygen concentration for fish is achieved at 4 ppm. So, water quality is good for aquatic life. Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) of water samples were determined by $BOD = DO_1 - DO_5$. During the study period, BOD were observed to be in the range of 0.23 to 0.60 ppm (Table 5). So the observed BOD values were < 5 ppm (UNEP Standard), which is within the permissible limit. COD was determined by potassium permanganate titration method. The COD values of water samples were found to be in the range of 28.0 to 31.2 ppm (Table 5). The standard value of COD for drinking water is 10 ppm (UNEP, 2004). Therefore, the higher values of COD were found to be in all samples.

In this study, toxic elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As and Cr) in three water samples were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (Table 6). The major sources of lead in drinking water are corrosion of household plumbing systems; and erosion of natural deposits (Chapman, 1996). Drinking water may not contain more than 0.05 ppm of lead. Lead contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.030 to 0.035 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were agreed with the standard value. Some people who drink water containing cadmium well in excess of the maximum contaminant level for many years could experience kidney damage. Maximum contaminant level of cadmium in drinking water is 0.005 ppm (WHO, 1996). The cadmium contents were not detected in all water samples. Most people have at least trace amounts of mercury in their tissues however it has been shown that high levels of mercury in the bloodstream of unborn babies and young children may harm the developing nervous system (Sundstrom and Keli, 1979). Maximum contaminant level of mercury in drinking water is 0.002 ppm. Mercury contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.0013 to 0.0015 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were agreed with the standard value.

Exposure to high levels of arsenic can cause cancers of the skin, bladder, kidney, and lung, and diseases of the blood vessels of the legs and feet. Diabetes, high blood pressure, and reproductive disorders have also been linked to arsenic exposure. Arsenic contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.077 to 0.089 ppm. Maximum contaminant level of arsenic in drinking water is 0.05 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were higher than the standard value. EPA has an enforceable drinking water standard of 0.1 mg/L for total chromium, which includes chromium-6 and chromium-3. Chromium contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.204 to 0.249 ppm. Therefore, the higher values of chromium contents were found to be in all samples.

Coliform organisms have long been recognized as a suitable microbial indicator of drinking-water quality, largely because they are easy to detect and enumerate in water (Salle, 1961). The term "coliform organisms" refers to Gram-negative, rod-shaped bacteria capable of growth in the presence of bile salts or other surface-active agents with similar growth-inhibiting

properties and able to ferment lactose at 35-37°C with the production of acid, gas, and aldehyde within 24–48 hours. They are also oxidase-negative and non-spore-forming and display β -galactosidase activity.

High bacteria counts in well water may be due to contamination from sources such as sewage treatment fields that are poorly designed, improperly constructed, failing, or located too close to the well (Soltys, 1963). High counts may also result from poor well construction (particularly in the case of old or shallow wells) or poor maintenance if the well is not properly protected from surface drainage water. Total coliforms contained in three water samples were determined by multiple tubes method in National Health Laboratory (NHL). It was found to be > 16 {total coliforms in MPN (Most Probable Number / 100 mL)}.

Table 1. Location of Sampling Site

Sample No.	Location	
	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)
1	20°31'36.23"	95°25'24.70"
2	20°31'44.57"	95°25'10.58"
3	20°30'56.07"	95°26'8.75"

Figure 1. Satellite image of sampling sites near Ywamon Village in Natmauk Township, Magway Region

Table 2. Determination of pH and Temperature in Water Samples

Sample	pH	Temperature (°C)
1	8.5	29.5
2	7.0	30.0
3	8.0	30.0
UNEP	6.5 - 8.5	0 - 60

Table 3. Determination of Total Alkalinity, Total Hardness, Chlorinity and Salinity in Water Samples

Sample	Total Alkalinity (ppm)	Total Hardness (ppm)	Chlorinity (ppm)	Salinity (ppt)
1	1320	265.6	92.19	0.190
2	480	255.1	53.19	0.125
3	970	318.8	241.13	0.465
UNEP	80 - 120	300	250	< 3

Table 4. Determination of Total Dissolved Solid and Total Suspended Solid in Water Samples

Sample	Total dissolved solid (ppm)	Total suspended solid (ppm)
1	360	700
2	900	600
3	2660	1100
UNEP	300	400

Table 5. Determination of Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) in Water Samples

Sample No.	Dissolved Oxygen (DO) (ppm)	Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) (ppm)	Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) (ppm)
1	7.11	0.60	30.4
2	4.53	0.51	28.0
3	6.11	0.23	31.2
UNEP	4 - 8	< 5.00	10.0

Table 6. Determination of Toxic Elements (Pb, Cd, Mg, As and Cr) in water samples

Sample No.	Pb Content (ppm)	Hg Content (ppm)	As Content (ppm)	Cr Content (ppm)
1	0.030± 0.009	0.0015±0.029	0.081± 0.025	0.215± 0.007
2	0.034± 0.023	0.0013±0.039	0.077± 0.051	0.204 ± 0.008
3	0.035± 0.018	0.0014±0.053	0.089± 0.037	0.249± 0.013
WHO Standard	0.05	0.002	0.05	< 0.1

Conclusion

In this research, three water samples were collected from Ywamon Village in Natmauk Township, Magway Region. Some physicochemical parameters and organic constituents of three water samples were determined.

The pH values of water samples were found in the range of 6.5 to 8.5. The pH values of all drinking water samples fall within the standard range.

Temperature of the water samples were found in the range of 29 to 30°C. It was found that the alkalinity values of water samples were found in the range of 480 to 1320 ppm. These values were very higher alkalinity in the samples. The chloride contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 53.19 to 241.13 ppm. The salinity contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.125 to 0.465 ppt. The chloride contents and salinity contents of water samples were found to be standard range.

The observed total hardness values of water samples were found to be in the range of 255.1 to 318.8 ppm. The high values of total hardness were found to be sample no. 3. The rest samples were agreed with the standard value. Total dissolved solids (TDS) values of water samples were found to be in the range of 360 to 2660 ppm. Thus, the determined values of samples were higher than the standard value. Total suspended solids of water samples were found to be in the range of 600 to 1100 ppm. Thus, the higher values of total suspended solids were found to be in all samples.

Dissolved oxygen contents of water samples were determined by DO meter and the values were found to be 4.53 to 7.11 ppm, which is within the permissible limit. During the study period, BOD were observed to be in the range of 0.23 to 0.60 ppm, which is within the permissible limit. The COD values of water samples were found to be in the range of 28.0 to 31.2 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were higher than the standard value.

In this study, toxic elements (Pb, Cd, Hg, As and Cr) in water samples were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Lead contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.030 to 0.035 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were agreed with the standard value. The cadmium contents were not detected in all water samples. Mercury contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.0013 to 0.0015 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were agreed with the standard value. Arsenic contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.077 to 0.089 ppm. Thus, the determined values of all samples were higher than the standard value. Chromium contents of water samples were found to be in the range of 0.204 to 0.249 ppm. Therefore, the higher values of chromium contents were found to be in all samples.

Total coliforms contained in three water samples were determined by multiple tubes method in National Health Laboratory (NHL). These were found to be > 16 MPN (Most Probable Number / 100 mL). These values were higher than the standard value, 10 MPN.

Due to the results, the pH values of all water samples were acceptable limit. The alkalinity values of these samples were very high. The higher values of total coliform were also found in all samples. The arsenic and chromium contents were higher in all samples. So it may be observed that these water samples should not be used as drinking water.

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